

Ileo-Sigmoid Knot: An Uncommon Surgical Emergency

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Abstract

The ileo-sigmoid knot (ISK) is a rare but life-threatening surgical emergency characterized by the simultaneous volvulus of the ileum and sigmoid colon, leading to acute intestinal obstruction. It is more common in certain regions of Africa, Asia, and the Middle East, with approximately 1,000 cases reported worldwide.

We report the case of a 50-year-old female with no significant past medical history who presented with symptoms of intestinal obstruction. Physical examination revealed abdominal distension and tenderness, and abdominal CT scan demonstrated the classic 'whirl sign' indicative of ISK with suspected ileal necrosis. Emergency laparotomy confirmed a double volvulus with necrosis of 2 meters of the ileum and a viable sigmoid colon. Surgical management involved resection of the necrotic ileal segment followed by primary anastomosis and sigmoidopexy.

Prompt diagnosis and surgical intervention are critical in managing ISK to prevent bowel necrosis and associated morbidity. Abdominal CT is essential for early detection, and treatment strategies depend on bowel viability. This case underscores the importance of considering ISK in patients presenting with acute intestinal obstruction, especially in regions with a higher prevalence.

Introduction

Ileo-sigmoid knot is a rare condition that occurs due to the wrapping of the ileum around the sigmoid colon. Initially described by Parker in 1845, it remains a rare cause of intestinal obstruction. This condition is more frequently observed in regions such as Africa and Asia, where anatomical factors like a long mesentery and dolichosigmoid are more prevalent [1-2].

The Case

We report the case of a 50 old year female without any significant past medical history, who was admitted in our department for an occlusive syndrome, without bleeding or any other sign.

Physical examination found the patient was conscious, afebrile (temperature: 37°C), with a heart rate of 110 beats per minute, blood pressure of 090/60 mmHg, respiratory rate of 23 breaths per minute, and oxygen saturation of 99% on room air. Her body mass index

(BMI) was 21 kg/m². Abdominal examination revealed a distended abdomen with general tenderness.

An Abdominal CT scan was realized showing: an important distension of small bowel and sigmoid with whirl sign with anomaly of vascularization of bowel suggesting necrosis of ileal (figure 1)

Biological test showed hemoglobin at 12.6 g/dL, hyperleukocytosis with WC at 28 450/mm³ albumin at 38 g/L, Na⁺ at 138 mEq/L, K⁺ at 4.1 mEq/L, urea at 0.47 g/L, and creatinine at 10.3 mg/L.

The patient underwent emergency laparotomy, which revealed a double volvulus involving the ileum and the sigmoid colon, with necrosis of approximately 2 meters of the ileum, while the sigmoid remained viable (Figure 2). Surgical management included resection of the necrotic small bowel, followed by primary anastomosis and sigmoidopexy.

The postoperative course was uneventful, and the patient was discharged home on postoperative day 5.

More Information

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Figure 1: CT Scan Images the Whirlpool Sign with Anomaly of Vascularization

Figure 2: Image Showing the Ileo-Sigmoid Knot with the Necrosis of the Ileum and a Viable Sigmoid

Discussion

The ileo-sigmoid knot is a surgical emergency characterized by a double volvulus involving the ileum and sigmoid colon, leading to simultaneous obstruction of both the small intestine and the sigmoid colon [2]. While rare in Western countries, it is relatively more common in parts of Africa, Asia, and the Middle East, where most reported cases originate. As of 2022, approximately 1,000 cases have been documented in the literature. The condition predominantly affects men between the ages of 30 and 60 [3]. Alveret al. [4] describes 4 types of double volvulus formation mechanism, depending on the active digestive segment responsible for the torsion:

- Type I: the ileum is the active segment wrapping around the passive sigmoid
- Type II results from the active sigmoid torsion attracting the passive small intestine

- Type III : the ileo-caecal junction that wraps around the sigmoid loop
- Type IV : the differentiation between the two segment is impossible

The clinical presentation of ileo-sigmoid knot is common to other intestinal obstruction, which include abdominal pain, abdominal distension, nausea, vomiting [5].

Abdominal CT scan is the key diagnostic tool for detecting an ileo-sigmoid knot. It typically reveals the characteristic ‘whirl sign,’ created by the twisting of the intestine and mesocolon. Additionally, the convergence of the afferent and efferent limbs of the sigmoid colon, along with the twisted mesentery and mesenteric vessels directed toward the pelvis, produces the so-called ‘beaking’ appearance [6].

Surgery is the cornerstone of treatment for ileo-sigmoid knot (ISK), as non-operative approaches such as endoscopic decompression are ineffective.

The surgical approach depends on the viability of the involved bowel segments. In cases where the ileum is necrotic, resection is necessary, followed by either primary anastomosis or the creation of an ostomy. If the sigmoid colon is necrotic, resection with a Hartmann's procedure is indicated. When both bowel segments are viable, management involves untying the knot, with various surgical options available. These include cecopexy, sigmoidopexy, sigmoid mesopexy, sigmoid mesoplasty, and sigmoid extraperitonealization. Some authors, however, advocate for sigmoid resection even in the absence of necrosis [7].

Conclusion

The ileo-sigmoid knot is a rare but serious cause of acute intestinal obstruction that requires prompt recognition and surgical management. Early diagnosis, often facilitated by characteristic CT findings such as the whirl sign, is crucial to prevent bowel necrosis and reduce morbidity. Surgical treatment must be tailored based on the viability of the involved bowel segments, with resection reserved for necrotic areas and various fixation techniques available when the bowel is viable. Awareness of this condition is essential, particularly in regions where it is more prevalent, to ensure timely intervention and improved patient outcomes.

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